
Monster UNet Architecture for Speech Enhancement

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Abstract

We propose a new UNet architecture for single-channel speech enhancement. On the competitive VCTK dataset, it achieves 3.18 PESQ, which establishes a new state-of-the-art amongst frequency-domain models.

1 Introduction

Speech enhancement is the task of enhancing a noisy audio sample so that the speech in it can be perceived more clearly. It is typically modeled as a problem of removing additive noise n from an audio sample x to recover the clean speech signal s .

$$x = s + n. \tag{1}$$

We can train a deep neural network for speech enhancement through supervised learning on pairs of x, s so that it learns the mapping from the noisy x to the clean s .

2 VCTK Benchmark

The VCTK dataset [1] is a popular benchmark for single-channel speech enhancement that contains pairs of noisy and clean speech, but with different conditions during training and test time to reflect the diversity of speech and noises found in the wild. Specifically, it features 28 speakers for training and 2 for testing, 10 noise types for training and 5 for testing, as well as 4 signal-to-noise ratios for training and 4 for testing. Importantly, there are no common speakers, noise types, or signal-to-noise ratios between the training and test set.

2.1 Pre-processing

The VCTK dataset does not contain a validation set, so we randomly subsample 1% of the training set to use for validation. We pre-process the data by down-sampling the audio samples from 48kHz to 16 kHz, and turn them into spectrograms using a 512-point STFT with a Hanning window of size 512 and hop size 256. This produces 257 frequency bins, of which we remove the last one to form inputs of size $64 \times 256 \times 1$.

3 Monster UNet

We propose a novel UNet architecture that we call *Monster UNet* for speech enhancement by scaling up prior UNet models found in the literature [2], and test it on the VCTK benchmark. The Monster UNet has 20,322,818 parameters in total throughout its 56 layers. The negative slope in the leaky ReLU is set to 0.2. The dropout rate is set to 0.1. $0.1 \ell_2$ -regularization is applied. We train it for 450 epochs with Adam using the settings in Bulut and Koishida [2]: learning rate 10^{-4} , $\beta = (0.5, 0.9)$, batch size 64, log-spectral distance loss. Full architectural details are given in Table 2.

4 Results

In Table 1, we report the mean performance of the Monster UNet across 5 random seeds, where testing is done on the model with the highest validation PESQ found at the end of training. Compared to other recent frequency-based methods found in the literature, our architecture achieves the best overall speech quality as measured by PESQ and COVL. Furthermore, it also recovers the highest fidelity of the clean speech signal as measured by COVL.

Table 1: Comparison with prior work on VCTK.

Method	Domain	PESQ	CSIG	COVL
MMSE-GAN [3]	Frequency	2.53	3.80	3.14
D+M [4]	Frequency	2.73	3.94	3.33
Low Latency UNet [2]	Frequency	2.90	4.22	3.58
T-GSA [5]	Frequency	3.06	4.18	3.62
Monster UNet	Frequency	3.18	4.49	3.91

References

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Table 2: Monster UNet Architecture

Layer	Kernel	Stride	Input	Input Shape	Output	Output Shape
Conv2d, BN, Dropout	7x7	1x1	Input	64x256x1	E0	64x256x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x2	E0	64x256x128	E1	64x128x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x1	E1	64x128x128	E2	64x128x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x2	E2	64x128x128	E3	64x64x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x1	E3	64x64x128	E4	64x64x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	E4	64x64x128	E5	64x32x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	E5	64x32x128	E6	64x32x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	E6	64x32x128	E7	64x16x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	E7	64x16x128	E8	64x16x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	E8	64x16x128	E9	64x8x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	E9	64x8x128	E10	64x8x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	E10	64x8x128	E11	64x4x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	E11	64x4x128	E12	64x4x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	E12	64x4x128	E13	64x2x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x2	1x1	E13	64x2x128	E14	64x2x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x2	1x2	E14	64x2x128	E15	64x1x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	E15	64x1x128	E16	64x1x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	E16	64x1x128	E17	32x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	E17	32x1x256	E18	32x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	E18	32x1x256	E19	16x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	E19	16x1x256	E20	16x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	E20	16x1x256	E21	8x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	E21	8x1x256	E22	8x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	E22	8x1x256	E23	4x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	E23	4x1x256	E24	4x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	E24	4x1x256	E25	2x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	2x1	1x1	E25	2x1x256	E26	2x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	2x1	2x1	E26	2x1x256	E27	1x1x512
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	1x1	2x1	E27	1x1x512	D27	2x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	2x1	1x1	Concat(D27, E26)	2x1x512	D26	2x1x256
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	2x1	2x1	Concat(D26, E25)	2x1x512	D25	4x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	Concat(D25, E24)	4x1x512	D24	4x1x256
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	Concat(D24, E23)	4x1x512	D23	8x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	Concat(D23, E22)	8x1x512	D22	8x1x256
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	Concat(D22, E21)	8x1x512	D21	16x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	Concat(D21, E20)	16x1x512	D20	16x1x256
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	Concat(D20, E19)	16x1x512	D19	32x1x256
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	Concat(D19, E18)	32x1x512	D18	32x1x256
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	2x1	Concat(D18, E17)	32x1x512	D17	64x1x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x1	Concat(D17, E16)	64x1x256	D16	64x1x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x1	1x2	Concat(D16, E15)	64x1x256	D15	64x2x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x2	1x1	Concat(D15, E14)	64x2x256	D14	64x2x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x2	1x2	Concat(D14, E13)	64x2x256	D13	64x4x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	Concat(D13, E12)	64x4x256	D12	64x4x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	Concat(D12, E11)	64x4x256	D11	64x8x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	Concat(D11, E10)	64x8x256	D10	64x8x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	Concat(D10, E9)	64x8x256	D9	64x16x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	Concat(D9, E8)	64x16x256	D8	64x16x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	Concat(D8, E7)	64x16x256	D7	64x32x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x1	Concat(D7, E6)	64x32x256	D6	64x32x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	3x3	1x2	Concat(D6, E5)	64x32x256	D5	64x64x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x1	Concat(D5, E4)	64x64x256	D4	64x64x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x2	Concat(D4, E3)	64x64x256	D3	64x128x128
LReLU, Conv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x1	Concat(D3, E2)	64x128x256	D2	64x128x128
LReLU, SubpixelConv2d, BN, Dropout	5x5	1x2	Concat(D2, E1)	64x128x256	D1	64x256x128
LReLU, Conv2d	7x7	1x1	Concat(D1, E0)	64x256x256	D0	64x256x1